

ISSN: 0976-8165

THE CRITERION

An International Journal in English

BI-MONTHLY REFEREED AND INDEXED, OPEN ACCESS E-JOURNAL

The Criterion

October 2014 Vol. 5, Issue-5

5th Year of Open Access

Editor-In-Chief

Dr. Vishwanath Bite

Managing Editor

Mrs. Madhuri Bite

www.the-criterion.com

CONTENTS

Sr. No.	Author	Title of the Paper	PageNo.	PDF
01	Amrita Chowdhury	Citizenship in an Anti-British Asylum: Pondicherry (1790-93)	01-11	PDF
02	Anindya Sundar Paul & Dr. Shri Krishan Rai	Discursive Formation of Reality: A Foucauldian Perspective to Aruni Kashyap's The House with a Thousand Stories	12-25	PDF
03	Anita Ahmadi	An Age of Surfaces: The Importance of Being Earnest by Oscar Wilde	26-38	PDF
04	Anju Bala	Home and Identity V. S. Naipaul's A House for Mr. Biswas	39-43	PDF
05	P.L.L. Annapurna & Jyoti Luxmi Kashyap	Manifestation of Figures of Rhetoric in the Advertisements of Travel & Tourism Industry	44-61	PDF
06	Arif Hussain Reshi	Comparing Mira Bai with Lal Ded, and Habba Khatoon	62-67	PDF
07	Balkar Singh	Mimicry of Hegemonic Discourses by Subalterns: Discourse Analysis of Kiran Desai's The Inheritance of Loss	68-73	PDF
08	Bharti Silswal	Asphyxiating Patriarchy and Polemical Misogyny in Guy De Maupassant's Useless Beauty	74-80	PDF
09	P. Bindhu & Dr. Ruby Davaseeli	Arundhati Roy and Jhumpa Lahiri as the Interpreters of 'The Small Things'	81-85	PDF
10	Cheena Chawla	Female Quest for a Self	86-89	PDF

		through Acts of Transgression: A Study of Jane Eyre and The Scarlet Letter		
11	Dr. Chinnadevi Singadi	Connotations of Rushdie's Midnight's Children and Khaled Hosseini's The Kite Runner	90-94	PDF
12	Darsha Jani	Historical Imagination and Anachronism in Walter Scott's The Heart of Midlothian	95-99	PDF
13	Dr. Pauline Das & L. Mohan Raj	Irula Folk Tales	100-107	PDF
14	Dr. Dhruv Shankar	Political Imagination in Graham Greene's The Comedians	108-113	PDF
15	Fareeha Khan	Otherness and Gender Identity in Sara Suleri's Meatless Days	114-124	PDF
16	Garima & Kusum Gulia	Emerging Trends in English Language Teaching	125-131	PDF
17	Dr. Dashrath Gatt	Edward Albee's Who's Afraid of Virginia Woolf: A Journey from Separation to Communion	132-138	PDF
18	Dr. Gulfishaan Habeeb	African American Autobiography	139-144	PDF
19	Archana Hooda	Fault Lines: An Immigrant Woman's Quest for a Homeland	145-153	PDF
20	Dr. Jayanta Mukherjee	Moral Education of the Protagonists in George Eliot's Felix Holt	154-157	PDF
21	Jennifer Monteiro	Decoding the Role of the Reader in The Murder of Roger Ackroyd: A Study in Popular Culture	158-161	PDF

22	Dr. Kavya B.	Women and Marriage in Anita Nair's <i>Ladie's Coupe</i>	162-171	PDF
23	Khushbu Trehan	Munro's Boys and Girls: A Portrayal of the Lives of Girls and Women	172-178	PDF
24	Naveen Kumar Kottidi	English Newspaper as an ESL Tool: A Study into Language Veracity	179-186	PDF
25	Y. Kusuma Kumari	Themes in the Recent Novels of Shashi Deshpande with Reference to <i>Small Remedies</i> , <i>Moving On</i> and <i>In the Country of Deceit</i>	187-193	PDF
26	Dr. Madhuri Sood	Spiritual Values in R. K. Narayan's Novels	194-196	PDF
27	Manisha Devi	Shakespeare's <i>Romeo and Juliet</i> : A Communicative Play	197-200	PDF
28	Manjinder Kaur Wratch	"Your History Comes in the Way of My Memory": An Inside Memory; Outside History Counter-Narrative of Partition	201-208	PDF
29	Manjushree. M.	Poetry across Borders: Blending Passion, Pain and Protest	209-215	PDF
30	Dr. Milan Swaroop Sharma	<i>The White Tiger</i> : A Study of Moral Recalcitrance	216-221	PDF
31	Mohamed Noufal N.	Notions of Caste, Gender and Class Hierarchies: Reading Postcolonial Indian Literatures and Cinema	222-227	PDF
32	Dr. Monika	<i>So Many Hungers!</i> : True Representation of Pre and Post Independent Hunger and Poverty Ridden India	228-232	PDF
33	V. Muralidharan & Dr. S. Ramamurthy	Shavian Humanism: A Bird's Eye View	233-244	PDF
34	G. Muthulaxmi	Unraveling Edith in Anita	245-249	PDF

		Brookner's Hotel du Lac		
35	Nisha Gangan	Celie in The Color Purple: Tracing Her Journey to Emancipation and Selfhood	250-256	PDF
36	Pratibha Patel	Interrogating Immigrant Experiences: A Global Perspective in Manju Kapur's The Immigrant	257-263	PDF
37	Purnima Bali	Portrayal of Women Characters in Rabindranath Tagore's The Garden	264-266	PDF
38	Raghavendra Nayak	The Conception of Facsimile: an Eco-critical Perspective in Snyder's Turtle Island	267-271	PDF
39	Rajani Devi	Historical Analysis of Gurcharan Das's Larins Sahib	272-276	PDF
40	Rajkumar Halder	Walter Morel: Irresponsible or Responsibility Distrusted	277-280	PDF
41	Ranjeet Kaur	The Image of Broken Marriages and Families in Shobha De's Socialite Evenings and Starry Nights	281-291	PDF
42	Dr. Abha Pandey & Rinkoo Wadhera	Hyper-Masculinity and Gender Stratification in Chinua Achebe's Things Fall Apart	292-296	PDF
43	Rozy Gupta & Dr. Tanu Gupta	Narrative Voice: A Study of Amitav Ghosh's The Glass Palace	297-302	PDF
44	Nesha Sabar	Ecocritical Readings and Descriptions of Landscape in Amitav Ghosh's Sea of Poppies and River of Smoke	303-310	PDF
45	Sanjay Kumar & Surjit Singh	Feminist Consciousness in Contemporary Haryanvi Short Stories	311-319	PDF
46	Santosh Prasad	The Theme of Alienation in	320-322	PDF

		Anita Desai's Cry, the Peacock		
47	S. Sheeba	Expressionism in Sean O' Casey's The Silver Tassie	323-331	PDF
48	Sheenam	The Hungry Tide: A Blend of Historico-Environmental Concerns	332-346	PDF
49	Shuv Raj Rana Bhat	The God of Small Things: Celebration of Mininarratives	347-351	PDF
50	Soumya Sangita Sahoo	Working for Nothing: Creation of Wage-free Jobs for the Australian Stolen Generations	352-358	PDF
51	Dr. Sutanu Kumar Mahapatra	The Aesthetics of Falsehood: Reading Marlowe's Protagonist in The Jew of Malta in the Light of Kierkegaard's Philosophy	359-364	PDF
52	Tamil Selvan C.	Existential Conflict in Bama's Karukku	365-367	PDF
53	Tanmay Chatterjee	Small World Proceedings: A Study of the Conference Papers, Lectures and Literary Discourses in David Lodge's Small World	368-374	PDF
54	Tazanfal Tehseem & Sidra Amir	Exploring the Construal of Death Victims in News Headlines: A Case Study	375-396	PDF
55	Vandana Ravi	Sakuni in the Mahabharata and Iago in Othello: Epitomes of Subtle Villainy	397-401	PDF
56	Vani Khurana	Multi-Faceted Reclusion as Women's Destiny in Fire on the Mountain	402-406	PDF
57	P. Vijaya Kumar & Dr. Lakshmidhar Dwivedi	Thematic Concerns in Arun Joshi's The Foreigner: A Critical View	407-413	PDF

Poetry

01	Ameen Fayaz	On the Razdan Heights	414-417	PDF
02	G David Schwartz	Waiting For the Road to End	418	PDF
03	Diane Dehler	Mount Vesuvius	419	PDF
04	Dorian Dyer	Forgotten Twilights	420	PDF
05	Gabriel Bamgbose	Where Do We Go When We Die?	421	PDF
06	A. P. Govindankutty	Kite	422	PDF
07	P. R. Jael Persis	Being Human Counts	423	PDF
08	John Szabo	Particles of Me	424	PDF
09	Mohammad Ehsanul Islam Khan	Story of Being Lost	425	PDF
10	Kusumita Mukherjee	Great Indian Game	426-427	PDF
11	Naresh Annem	Love Letter	428-430	PDF
12	Parminder Singh	Simile	431	PDF
13	Pratima Annapurna Balabhadrapathruni	Echolocation	432-433	PDF
14	Dr. Rajnish Mishra	My Kashi	434	PDF
15	Dr. Abdullah Shaghi	Soul's Planet	435-436	PDF
16	Dr. Shalini Yadav	Motherhood's Triumph	437-438	PDF
17	Dr. Simmi Gurwara	A Woman of Substance	439-440	PDF
18	E. Smith Sleight	Ecotone	441-442	PDF
19	Sonika Jaggi	Predestination	443-444	PDF
20	Soumya Sangita Sahoo	Indulgence	445-447	PDF
21	Suchishraba Sarangi	The Last Minute....	448	PDF
22	Thomas Piekarski	Balancing Act	449	PDF
23	Yoshira	Time	450	PDF
24	Changming Yuan	Dayatoola	451	PDF

Fiction

01	Gagan Bihari Purohit	Savitri	452-456	PDF
02	Navaneeta	Threshold	457-459	PDF
03	Ramil Jayson L.	Elisa's Short Story	460-461	PDF

	Soriano			
04	Junaid Rashid	The 'Grave' Incident	462-464	PDF
Book Review				
01	Sagarika Dash	Binodini by Krishna Kripalani	465-467	PDF
02	Shahzia Batool Naqvi	Canvas and Colours by Ramakanta Das	468-471	PDF
03	Dr. Y. Vijaya Babu	Yet, I am Not Defeated by Jyothi Reddy	472-473	PDF